

Synthetic pyrethroids for caseworm control, Aduthurai, India, 1984.^a

Insecticide	Formulation (EC)	Dose (g ai/ha)	Damaged leaves before treatment (%)	Mortality ^b (%) after	
				24 h	48 h
Fenvalerate	20	100	81	97 a	91 a
	20	15	81	94 ab	94 a
Cypermethrin	25	80	80	95 a	91 a
	25	60	66	95 ab	94 a
Deltamethrin	2.8	15	82	94 ab	95 a
	2.8	11.25	90	91 ab	92 a
Endosulfan (standard check)	35	500	78	81 b	81 b
Untreated check			86	6 c	5 c

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

caseworm control. IR50 was planted in 40 m².

Pretreatment caseworm damage was recorded on 12 randomly selected hills/plot. Damage between plots did not significantly differ. Results were recorded by counting live and dead larvae 24 and 48 h after treatment.

All pyrethroid treatments were superior to the control and the standard check (see table). Fenvalerate 20 EC sprayed at 100 g ai/ha gave 97% mortality at 24 and 48 h after treatment. *J*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Survey of rodents and rodent damage in deep water rice

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We studied rodent activity in several deep water rice fields at Huntra Station, Ayutthaya Province, from Mar 1984 to Feb 1985. One hundred live traps baited with fresh fish were set on 3 consecutive nights at 4-6 wk intervals. In the same fields, stem damage caused by rodents was estimated several times. During the deepest flooding, a large, adjacent field also was sampled.

Rats *Bandicota indica*, *Rattus losea*, and *Rattus argentiventer* were active in the fields. Rat populations were influenced by food availability and floodwater level (see figure). At peak flooding, when all dikes were submerged, we trapped no *R. argentiventer*, but the other species remained active. *B. indica* and *R. losea* continued to live and reproduce in the field. Stem cutting by rats began in Jun and continued through stem elongation at 95 cm water depth. The cumulative seasonal damage probably exceeded 10% of the stems. *J*

Species composition and numbers of rats, Huntra, Thailand, 1984-85. The dashed bars shown for Oct represent rat numbers in an adjacent farmer's field.

Soil and Crop Management

Nitrogen fertilizer efficiency in two major rice soils of Bangladesh

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We evaluated N fertilizer efficiency in

Grey Floodplain (Mymensingh) and Red Brown Terrace (Madhupur) soils in Bangladesh in boro, aus, and transplanted aman. BR-3 was planted at both sites. Soil at Mymensingh was a silt loam with pH 6.8, 0.57% organic C, CEC and exchangeable K 9.2 and 0.25